

Adsorption of Stearic Acid on Pure and Mixed Oxides

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The adsorption of stearic acid from solutions in cyclohexane on tin oxide (in the form of gel and precipitate), antimony oxide and tin antimony mixed oxides having various ratios of tin to antimony, has been investigated. It is observed that the mode of adsorption depends upon the surface acidity of the oxide. In the case of tin oxide gel, tin oxide ppt. and the mixed oxides with Sb : Sn as 1 : 5 and 1 : 10, stearic acid is adsorbed with its hydrocarbon chain parallel to the surface. With antimony oxide and mixed oxides with higher percentage of antimony, the perpendicular orientation is adopted.

THE adsorption of long chain fatty acids from solutions in organic solvents has frequently been used for evaluating surface characteristics of solids¹. It has been observed that stearic acid adsorbs itself from its solutions in cyclohexane parallel to the surface of homogeneous carbons. A similar orientation is preferred by stearic acid from its solutions in inert solvents on silica². But it has been reported that a perpendicular orientation is adopted by the long-chain fatty acids on alumina and titania¹⁻².

It is revealed on perusal of literature that adsorption studies on tin oxide and antimony oxide have not been carried out to an appreciable extent. Some recent studies have proved that tin oxide, antimony oxide and their mixtures act as efficient and highly selective catalysts in a number of industrial processes particularly the dehydrogenation of olefins³. Surface area, surface acidity, particle size, conductivity measurements⁴ and solid state studies⁵ have been used to characterise the surface of the active solids. In order to obtain more information about the nature of the surface of these oxides, it was thought of interest to study the orientation of stearic acid adsorbed onto tin oxide (gel and precipitate), antimony oxide and their co-precipitated mixtures having varying percentages of Sn and Sb. Similar adsorption studies form n-hexane-benzene⁶, alcohol-hydrocarbon⁷ and fatty acid hydrocarbon⁸ solutions has been reported earlier. In the present paper, the observed adsorption values have been compared with the values calculated on the basis of various orientations. For one of the samples (SnO₂ gel), the composite isotherm has been analysed by the Schay and Nagy⁹ method to yield the individual adsorption isotherms.

Experimental

Preparation of materials. The oxide gel was prepared by mixing equal volumes of 1.2 N ammonia solution and 1.0 N solution of stannic chloride⁴. Tin oxide and antimony oxides were prepared by treating pure tin and antimony metals separately with conc.

nitric acid and washing the products with distilled water till free from NO₃⁻ ions. Mixed oxides were prepared in a similar way by treating calculated quantities of tin and antimony metals with conc. nitric acid. All these samples except tin oxide gel were dried in an air oven at 120°. Tin oxide gel was air dried at 30°. All the solids were passed through a 100 mesh sieve to maintain uniformity in their particle size. Cyclohexane was purified by distillation and the fraction distilling at 81° was collected. Cyclohexane was chosen as a solvent to minimise the interaction between the solvent and the adsorbent. TGA analysis of the samples was done on Stanton balance. The stoichiometry of the mixed oxides was confirmed by usual analytical methods¹⁰. The acidity of the samples was determined by adsorption of barium hydroxide in aqueous solution (Table 3).

Adsorption studies

One g. of the sample was mixed with 10 ml. of the stearic acid solution, of varying concentrations in cyclohexane in each bottle which was sealed and kept in an air-oven maintained at 30 ± 1°. The bottles were shaken occasionally. Reference solutions were also treated in a similar manner. After 24 hours, bottles were unsealed and stearic acid solutions were analysed titrimetrically using hot ethyl alcohol. Adsorption results for the samples are plotted in figs 1-2 in the form of composite isotherms.

Results and Discussion

Tin oxide gel, tin oxide, antimony oxide and mixed oxides were subjected to TGA. In the case of tin oxide gel the results showed a gradual loss of weight from 150 to 600°, thereafter the weight remained unchanged upto 1000°. The loss in weight as reported in case of silica and alumina gels indicates the presence of —OH groups on the surface which on heating decompose to lose H₂O leaving behind =O groups. In case of tin oxide, antimony oxide and mixed oxides, no loss was recorded from 150 to 1000°, which indicated the absence

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of OH groups and presence of oxygen as = 0. The nature of surface thus revealed by TGA for the various samples is given in Table.

Fig. 1. Adsorption of stearic acid from solutions in cyclohexane.

- (a) SnO₂ gel
- (b) SnO₂ precipitate
- (c) Sb₂O₅

Fig. 2. Adsorption of stearic acid from solutions in cyclohexane.

- (a) 10SnO₂.Sb₂O₅
- (b) 10SnO₂. $\frac{1}{3}$ Sb₂O₅
- (c) 2SnO₂.5Sb₂O₅
- (d) SnO₂.5Sb₂O₅

TABLE I—SURFACE AREA AND NATURE OF SURFACE INDICATED BY T.G.A. STUDIES

S. No.	Sample	Surface area from N ₂ adsorption (m ² /g)	Nature of the surface (T.G.A. Studies)
1	SnO ₂ gel	160	Complete coverage of -OH groups
2	Sb ₂ O ₅	16	=O group only
3	10 SnO ₂ .Sb ₂ O ₅	130	
4	10 SnO ₂ . $\frac{1}{3}$ Sb ₂ O ₅	140	
5	SnO ₂ .5Sb ₂ O ₅	6.2	-O group only
6	2 SnO ₂ .5Sb ₂ O ₅	29.4	
7	SnO ₂ ppt	100.00	

Stearic acid is known to be present in the dimeric form¹ in cyclohexane over the whole concentration range used. The mole fractions of the equilibrium solution have been calculated by using the molecular weight of the dimer. As reported by Kipling¹¹ the

surface excess of component I is given by the following equation which is based on the material balance :

$$n_0 \Delta x_1 / m = n_1^2 (1 - x_1) - n_2^2 x_1 \quad (1)$$

where Δx_1 is the change in the mole fraction of the component 1 in the bulk phase which takes place when m grams of the adsorbent are brought into contact with n₀ moles of the liquid, x₁ is the mole fraction of the component 1 in the bulk phase at equilibrium and n₁² and n₂² are the number of moles of components 1 and 2 respectively adsorbed per g. of the solid. The composite isotherm does not give us the true adsorption of solute, but equation 1 in combination with equation 2, as suggested by Schay and Nagy⁹, can be used to calculate n₁² and n₂² :

$$\frac{n_1^2}{(n_1)_m} + \frac{n_2^2}{(n_2)_m} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where (n₁)_m and (n₂)_m are numbers of moles of stearic acid and cyclohexane respectively required to form a monolayer on the adsorbent. The molecular area for cyclohexane has been taken as 45°A². The results for a typical case are shown in figure 3. From the

Fig. 3. Individual adsorption isotherms (on tin oxide gel) of (a) stearic acid, (b) cyclohexane, (c) is the composite isotherm for the adsorption of stearic acid.

composite isotherms, it is possible to obtain a limiting value of adsorption from an obvious plateau in the isotherm¹. These limiting values are compared in Table 2 with calculated monolayer values based on the two orientations for stearic acid with molecular areas (expressed in terms of monomeric molecules) of 114A² for parallel orientation and 20.5A² for perpendicular orientation as reported in the literature¹³. As these molecular areas differ by a factor of approximately five, there is no difficulty in deciding about the orientation actually adopted.

In the case of SnO₂ gel, the ratio of observed monolayer value to calculated monolayer value based on parallel orientation comes out to be 0.9. This proves that stearic acid is adsorbed on the surface of SnO₂ gel in parallel orientation. Similar is the case

TABLE 2

Sample	Calc. monolayer value (millimoles of monomer per g)		Limiting Obs. value (m moles/g)	Rate of Obs. to Calc. value
	Perpendicular orientation	Parallel orientation		
SnO ₂ gel	—	.23	.21	0.90
SnO ₂ ppt	—	.146	.141	0.96
Sb ₂ O ₃	0.13	—	.065	0.5
SnO ₂ .5Sb ₂ O ₃	0.05	—	.04	0.8
2SnO ₂ .5Sb ₂ O ₃	0.24	—	.12	0.5
10SnO ₂ .Sb ₂ O ₃	—	0.18	.146	0.8
10SnO ₂ . $\frac{1}{3}$ Sb ₂ O ₃	—	0.2	.15	0.75

with SnO₂ ppt where the ratio of observed monolayer to calculated monolayer value based on parallel orientation is 0.96. In the case of antimony oxide the ratio of observed monolayer value to the calculated monolayer value based on perpendicular orientation comes out to be 0.5. It is consistent with the findings in the literature¹ that in perpendicular orientation, a complete monolayer is never formed as the adsorption takes place at specific sites by hydrogen bonding or in some cases by chemisorption as well. The ratio of observed to calculated monolayer values in such cases depends upon the spacing of such sites.

In the case of mixed oxide with Sb:Sn = 10:1 and 5:1 (sample no. 7,8, Table 1), perpendicular orientation is maintained. But the things are reversed when we go to mixed oxides in which Sb to Sn ratio is 1:5 and 1:10 i.e. samples no. 5 and 6 respectively. In these cases because SnO₂ is the major constituent, parallel orientation is adopted. This is revealed by the ratios of observed monolayer values to values calculated on the basis of parallel orientation which come out to be 0.8 and 0.75 respectively.

In cases where parallel orientation is adopted, the observed monolayer value generally falls short of the calculated monolayer value. This may be ascribed to the some amount of solvent in the adsorbed layer where the ratio is 0.9 or 0.96. But the ratios 0.75 or 0.8 can not be explained on the basis of this plea. Assumption of the hydrocarbon chain inclined at some angle instead of being completely flat would perhaps be the satisfactory interpretation.

In the case of SnO₂ gel and Sb₂O₃, the isotherms show a steep rise towards the solubility limit. It is due to phase crystallisation of stearic acid that takes place in this region^{1,2}. It is similar to phase separation^{2,3} that takes place in the case of adsorption of liquid solutes from their solutions by silica and alumina catalysts.

The orientation adopted by stearic acid has a direct bearing with the polarity of the surface. The more polar the surface, greater is the tendency for perpendicular orientation. This is evident from Table 3 which gives the surface acidity, for the samples as found out by barium hydroxide adsorption. SnO₂ gel, SnO₂ and mixed oxides with Sb to Sn ratio 1:5 and 1:10 have lower surface acidities (column 3, Table 3). Therefore stearic acid prefers a parallel orientation on these surfaces. On the other hand Sb₂O₃ and mixed oxides, in which Sb to Sn ratio is 10:1 and 5:1, have surface polarity of the higher order; thereby adsorbing stearic acid in perpendicular orientation probably due to higher heat of adsorption.

TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL AND NORMALISED BASE ADSORPTION VALUES OF THE ADSORBENTS

Sample	Surface acidity Ba(OH) ₂ adsorption value (m. equivalent/g)	Base adsorption value (After normalising for surface area) m. eq/100 m ²
SnO ₂ gel	0.85	0.53
SnO ₂ ppt	1.54	1.54
Sb ₂ O ₃	1.10	7.00
SnO ₂ .5Sb ₂ O ₃	1.19	20.00
2SnO ₂ .5Sb ₂ O ₃	1.29	3.90
10SnO ₂ .Sb ₂ O ₃	1.70	1.30
10SnO ₂ . $\frac{1}{3}$ Sb ₂ O ₃	1.66	1.20

For a system with a sufficiently low solubility limit as in this case, the individual isotherm would be indistinguishable from the composite isotherm within the limits of experimental error (c.f. figure 3a as individual isotherm and 3c as composite 'sotherm').

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